

Numerology and Archeoastronomy, Borobudur and Angkor Wat

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“Numerology, in the sense of constructing meaningful relationships between numerical patterns and concepts as a way of understanding the world, ... is regularly observed amongst non-Western societies” (Darvill, 2023). Stimulated by Darvill’s words, in a work published in January 2024, I proposed the study of the influence of numerology on landscape and architecture design. In particular, the work focused on monuments containing 108 architectonic and decorative elements, in the framework of their cultural landscapes. Number 108 is highly relevant in Buddhism and Hinduism, and consequently the related architectures show the presence of 108 elements (shrines, stupas, statues). Among the considerable monumental sites, we find the well-known Angkor Thom, Angkor Wat and Candi Borobudur. For these sites, it is now necessary to further stress the numerology in literature, also related to the zenith passage of the sun. Moreover, in an archaeoastronomical framework, the possible alignments of architectures with the sun path above them is here considered in the same literature too. Specific attention will be devoted to calendars in Java, and analogous Mayan calendars.

Why numerology? Why number 108?

Numerology is often associated with the term ‘pseudo-science’. Then, it is fundamental to assume numerology in the sense used by Timothy Darvill. In 2023, [he opposed](#) to this generic assertion the fact that “Numerology, in the sense of constructing meaningful relationships between numerical patterns and concepts as a way of understanding the world, ... is regularly observed amongst non-Western societies”. Actually, Timothy Darvill, 2022, in his [‘Keeping time at Stonehenge’](#) used the term ‘numerology’, for the numbering of the Sarsen stones and the four stones of the [Quadrangle](#), to show that Stonehenge, in his opinion, was a monumental version of a calendar. He used the term ‘numerology’ three times in his work, without specifying what he intended with this term. In fact, I understood Darvill’s numerology as the numbering of stones. Being this ‘numerology’ related to a monumental calendar, was there also a ritual practiced by Stonehenge people according to numbers?

The three-time mentioned ‘numerology’ sparked a vehement reaction. Instead of asking Darvill: “What do you mean by ‘numerology’? Please explain”, it has been said that numerology is the “pseudo-scientific way of reasoning” that tends to find links between “numbers and concepts”. And also, that “in many *fringe* publications” we can find that Angkor Wat is 72° east of Giza, “because 72 are the years required to complete a degree of the precessional movement of the Earth”. It seems absurd to report these sentences, but they are what Darvill saw written against. Cambogia, Giza, and precession have nothing to do with Stonehenge (the argument borders a ‘straw man’ fallacy).

HERE we are not supporting any link between number 72 and the Earth’s precession. ***And this will be evident when we report literature.***

Consider please carefully, in reading my discussion about numerology and archaeoastronomy, that we are contemplating the architectonic elements of the monuments in Cambogia and Java. ***HERE***, we are ***doing science*** in the sense that we are evidencing the number of the architectonic elements and their cultural substrate. That is, ***we are here doing numerology possessing a cultural background.***

Archaeoastronomer Anthony Aveni had a similar approach.

Let us read Samalavicius, (2011). “Attempts to solve the mystery of the universe are often related to the teaching of Pythagoreans, but as Aveni has remarked, all cultures of the world share the same quality – they attempt to seek balance and harmony no matter how geographically remote they are. In a penetrating essay, *Aveni discusses the numerology of the Mayan civilization*, and reveals that the Mayan people reasoned in the same way as the ancient Greeks, believing that the basic instruments of the universe’s sounds are the Sun and the Moon. ...” (Samalavicius, 2011). “As it is for all societies that base their time count on the repetition of natural phenomenon, euphonic concurrence with cyclical periods of nature was extremely important” (Samalavicius mentioning Aveni, “Is Harmony at the Heart of Things?). Here the permanent link <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40260149>, Aveni, 2001.

Is Harmony at the Heart of Things?

Virtually all civilizations, from the Greek and the ancient Mayan to our own, are united by a determined quest for evidence of harmony in the cosmos.

by Anthony Aveni

It is fundamental to investigate what really told the Pythagoreans and how Aveni linked Greek and Mayan civilizations.

“Numerology, in the sense of constructing meaningful relationships between numerical patterns and concepts as a way of understanding the world, may not be to [someone's] ‘scientific’ taste, but it is regularly observed amongst non-Western societies when building calendars and giving order to the cosmos. Many of the case studies unfolded in Nilsson's (1920) classic study of primitive time-reckoning provide examples, while Crump's (1992) study takes a wider historical perspective.” (Darvill, 2023).

It is true that non-Western societies permeated their architecture with specific numbers. For instance, in [Sparavigna 2024](#), it is considered architectures and number 108. Why 108? This is a question that we can find in the Olsen's “Sacred places around the world: 108 destinations”, 2004. “Numbers, it can be argued, carry as much significance as letters. Numbers convey a different method of communication altogether, forming the basis for commerce and all the sciences. Numbers are deeply rooted in many cultural traditions, oftentimes contemporary with a civilization’s original literary works. Such is the case with the number 108 in most East Asian religious cultures. 108 is the number of beads on sacred mala necklaces worn by millions of reverent Buddhists and Hindus. To them, the number 108 is associated with the precessionary cycles of earth and the cosmos above” (Olsen, 2004). Precessionary? See please what I said previously. Here, I do not consider Earth’s precession.

In my [SSRN 2024](#), the reader starts visiting a place in China, where we can admire [One Hundred and Eight Stupas](#) (see references given in SSRN; for instance, Lei, 1996). The place is at Qingtongxia, coordinates 37°52'27"N 105°58'43"E. This site is remarkable for the number of stupas. Why 108 stupas? This is the first question that we must ask ourselves because the number of stupas is the first feature that we observe when we are in front of this monument. Archeoastronomy, – the other subject of our discussion –, considers alignments that can add further information, but the number is the most relevant character of the monument. In green archeoastronomy, the “common source of data ... is the study of alignments. This *is based on the assumption* that the *axis of alignment* of an archaeological site is *meaningfully oriented* towards an astronomical target” ([Wikipedia](#)). However, we have learned that alignments are not enough to justify conclusions about the considered sites, in particular for what is regarding the Roman world (see the discussion about [the Roman Town and the Templum](#)). *An alignment does not automatically ensure a datum of evidential nature*. Moreover, non-Western monuments require numerology, whether archaeoastronomers like it or not.

After the 108 stupas of Qingtongxia, in [SSRN 2024](#), the reader can find the ‘Gobi’s spiritual power’ (Croft, 2023), that is sites of Gobi desert, and then visit the Erdene Zuu Monastery. Thanks to the Dochula Pass, and with a huge imaginary voyage, from Himalaya we arrived at Borobudur, Java.

Borobudur, Java

“Candi Borobudur (Borobudur Temple) is the world’s largest Mahayana Vajrayana Buddhist temple, which is located in Magelang, Central Java, Indonesia. It was built by the Sailendra dynasty between the 8th and 9th centuries A.D. The temple was built with 10-step pyramid terraces, which are decorated with 2,672 relief panels, 504 Buddha statues, and 1,537 stupas. . . . The stupas at Borobudur located from the second to ninth terraces are called the secondary stupas, whereas the one located on the tenth terrace is called the primary stupa. They are symbolic stupas, which consist of a base (Prasadha), a bell-shaped body (anda), a top support (harmika), and a top (yashti). The stupas are divided into four types, namely plain stupas, hollow space-square stupas, hollow space-diamond stupas containing the Dhyani Buddha Vairocana that represents the turning wheel of the dharma and the single main stupa that becomes the centre of Borobudur. Temple is reflecting Sailedra art-style.” (Revianur, 2017).

Fig. 1: Borobudur Temple in 2013. Courtesy Kartika Sari Henry, Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Borobudur#/media/File:Borobudur_Temple.jpg .

Fig. 2: Borobudur seen from above. Satellite image. Courtesy Google Earth.

Fig. 3. Stupas on the Borobudur platform. Image Courtesy Google Earth Street View.

“The main component of a Buddhist temple, including Borobudur, is the stupa. The stupa, in the period before Buddha, would have served as a tomb and later became the symbol of Buddha’s life. It was originally built to bury the relics of Buddha shortly after his body was cremated. In its further development, a stupa was used to store not only the relics of Buddhist monks but also Buddhist objects. ... A stupa, which describes the concept of Buddhism, has several sections, namely the basis of the stupa (Prasadha), the parts of the ball (dagob) or bell (genta) and the top or crown (yashti)” (Revianur, 2017).

Of this temple and of the sun zenith passage above it, we discussed in February and May 2017 (Sparavigna, 2017). Mentioning a possible calendrical role. On the uppermost platform of Candi Borobudur, we can see 72 stupas (see Fig.3), dedicated to the Zenith direction. In February 2017, we observed that 72 is also the number of days passing from the zenith passage of October 12 to the December solstice, and from December solstice to the zenith passage on the end of February (or first of March). The same number, 72, is observed for the Sewu and Prambanan temples too. These temples and the Candi (temple) Borobudur are in Java. In May 2017, we stressed that a pure religious interpretation of the seventy-two temples of the Sewu central structure existed, as for those of Borobudur. “Within the Buddhist Abhidharma philosophical schools”, there are “three unconditioned Dharmas whose nature is free from the laws of causation (asamskrta) as well as 72 conditioned Dharmas, which are subject to the laws of causation (samskrta). So one might conjecture that these 72 auxiliary shrines [at Sewu] had pertained to what Vilāsavajra had called the second circle of Mahāvairocana containing the divinities belonging to the perfectly pure Dharmadhātu of Vairocana” (Long, 2015). Being number 72 relevant in Buddhism and being this number also dedicated to the Zenith direction, we argued that the 72 days passing from the sun zenith passage and December solstice, and from solstice to the zenith passage at the end of February, could have been important for local people. In this manner, solstices and zenith passages could have been used to mark periods of the year.

Khan Academy

“Moving past the base and through the four galleries, the devotee emerges onto the three upper terraces, encountering 72 stupas each containing a three-dimensional sculpture of a seated Buddha within a stone latticework. At the temple’s apex sits the large central stupa, a symbol of the enlightened mind. ... The idea of moving from the darkness into the light is the final element of the experience of Borobudur. The

temple's pathway takes one from the earthly realm of desire (kamadhatu), represented and documented on the hidden narratives of the structure's earthbound base, through the world of forms (rupadhatu) as expounded on the narratives carved along the four galleries set at right angles, until one finally emerges into the realm of formlessness (arupadhatu) as symbolized and manifested in the open circular terraces crowned with 72 stupas. ... The crowning stupa of this sacred mountain is dedicated to the "Great Sun Buddha" Vairocana. The temple sits in cosmic proximity to the nearby volcano Mt. Merapi. During certain times of the year the path of the rising sun in the East seems to emerge out of the mountain to strike the temple's peak in radiant synergy" (R. E. Gordon, [Khan Academy](#)).

Fig.4: "Watching the sunrise over Borobudur", with morning mist and Merapi volcano, in picture Courtesy patrickdevries2003, https://www.flickr.com/photos/p_de_vries/28730946690/in/photostream/

Number 108 at Borobudur

What about number 108? Let us consider in detail stupas and statues of Borobudur to test if we can find in it also 108 units. Before illustrating the further numbers displayed by the temple, let us add some information. The temple is a site of pilgrimage. In it, the pilgrim can find the "biography of the Lord Buddha, ... , [which] is depicted on the main wall of the first gallery. ... In striking contrast to the square terraces of the rupadhatu, the circular platforms representing the Sphere of Formlessness are plain: no carvings, no ornaments, no embellishments. The only break in the monotonous plainness is offered by the row of stupas that encircle the big central dome. Supported by lotus cushions, the stupas

are arranged in three concentric circles, corresponding to the three circular platforms. In all there are 72 stupas: 32 on the lowest or first platform, 24 on the second and 16 on the third. Each of the 72 stupas has a kind of lattice-work surface, composed of stones and diamond-shaped empty spaces which partly disclose the seated Buddha statue inside” (Soekmono, 1976). And “the Borobudur statues show five kinds of mudra, corresponding to the five cardinal points of the compass (East, West, North, South, Zenith), and also to the Mahayana conception of the five Dhyani Buddhas. One point of the compass is ascribed to each Dhyani Buddha, and the distinction between the Dhyani Buddhas is indicated by the different mudras” (Soekmono, 1976).

We can find many illustrations of the Buddha’s life depicted on Borobudur walls in a book by Isaac Groneman, 1912. Groneman had a profound interest for the religious context of Candi Borobudur. He considered Borobudur as a Buddhist sanctuary, obtaining support by King Chulalongkorn, that we can find mentioned in Groneman's book entitled "Ruins of Buddhistic temples in Prägä valley: Tyandis Barabudur, Mendut and Pawon". In the title we find the word "tyandi", that is "candi", "temple". The book is a remarkable discussion of the three temples (Borobudur, Mendut, Pawon), which are linked by a ritual relationship and by an alignment - let us stress, supposed alignment - of the sites. The temples of Mendut and Pawon are thought to have been early purification temples for pilgrims going to Borobudur (Brockman, 2011).

On Vesak Day, a procession along the alignment of the temples goes from Mendut to Borobudur (Brockman, 2011). In his book, Groneman is following the same approach, and the first temple he discusses is Candi Mendut. That is, the Borobudur Temple Compound seems being made of three monuments: namely the Borobudur Temple and two smaller (ancillary) temples situated to the east on a straight axis to Borobudur (see the discussion about Four Temples). ***Let us stress that the first historically attested celebration of Vesak at Borobudur dates 1953*** (Chia, 2020).

From [The Borobudur Temple: A Cosmic Stupa, by Indosphere Culture, 2019, Medium](#). “The temple [Borobudur] is oriented to the four directions and is expanded vertically in accordance with Buddhist cosmology to construct the Universe in a small scale. There are all total four entrances and four complete steps for ascending the highest point from the lowest point from the four directions of East, South, West and North respectively to enter the monument..... Mendut Temple, whose depiction of Buddha is represented by a formidable monolith accompanied by two Bodhisattvas. Pawon Temple, a smaller temple whose inner space does not reveal which deity might have been the object of worship. Those three monuments represent phases in the attainment of Nirvana. During the full moon in May or June, Buddhists in Indonesia observe the Vesak annual ritual by walking from Mendut temple, past Pawon and then to Borobudur.”

Is number 108 present in Candi Borobudur? “Looking at all sides of Borobudur there are *108 Buddha statues in niches on each side facing each cardinal direction.*” (Kandahjaya, 2022). In Snellgrove, 1996, we can find that “the one and only Buddha manifests himself under a variety of names in all the directions of space. This idea is expressed admirably by the pattern of a mandala. ... as it is well known, this notion is eventually formalized as the basic set of Five Buddhas, representing the centre and four points of the compass, although it is assumed that their power of emanation is infinite. It is this stage of Mahayana development which we find represented on the great Borobudur stupa. The Buddhas of the four directions, Aksobhya (E), Ratnasambhava (S), Amitabha (W) and Amoghasiddhi (N) are represented on the four sides of the stupa, the auspicious number of 108 to each side. Vairocana (with his conventionalized hand-gesture of preaching) presides over the three upper circular terraces, manifest as eight such Buddha images on the upper terrace [actually it is four times four], 16 on the next lower one [six times four] and 32 on the lowest of the three [from Fig.4b, eight times four]. John Lundquist observes that this total number of 72 represents just twice the number of the 36 divinities (less the central divinity) of the Vajradhatu mandala” (Snellgrove, 1996). Stupas (see Fig.3b) are $4 \times 8 + 4 \times 6 + 4 \times 4 = 72$.

Fig. 5: Buddha statues and stupas at Borobudur. Image Courtesy reggaelooper, <https://pixabay.com/it/users/reggaelooper-3002941/>, under License <https://pixabay.com/it/service/license-summary/>

However, mentioning Lundquist's work, 1995, Snellgrove remarks that 72 are the manifestations "of the central Buddha Vairocana, whose popularity as Primary Buddha is well attested by many other images in commanding positions during the Sailendra period. It is certainly significant that he appears enthroned centrally in Candi Mendut, the important shrine visited by pilgrims on their way to Borobudur. There would seem to be nothing very special about the number 72, if these manifestations are simply regarded as the most obvious symmetrical lines of emanation from a fixed centre. The fact that they are all of Vairocana is certainly significant. We may then conceive of him as yet further dispersed to the four major directions as the 108 manifestations of each of the four well known Directional Buddhas. There is thus no need for any other specific supreme Buddha manifestation at the very centre of this stupa, and archaeological research has identified none with any certainty" (Snellgrove, 1996).

Let us stress that, being Java in the Tropical Zone, we have there the sun zenith passage. This can be a good reason to stress, also in the monuments, the fundamental role of Vairocana.

The five Buddhas are therefore linked to what is "the spatial form of a circle with a center, a form that would imply the four cardinal directions with a center (zenith/nadir)" (Rhie, 2019). In Snodgrass, 2018, in a discussion about the symbolism of the stupa, we can find a table reporting the correlations of the five Buddhas, the directions, the types of consciousness and the aspect of Knowledge.

	Direction	Consciousness	Knowledge
Vairocana	Center or Zenith	Undefined Consciousness	Knowledge of the Essential Nature of the Dharma World
Aksobhya	East	Storehouse Consciousness	Mirror Knowledge
Ratnasambhava	South	Mind Consciousness	Knowledge of the Identity of Essences
Amitābha	West	Thought Consciousness	Knowledge of Wondrous Perception
Amoghasiddhi	North	Sense Consciousness: Sight Taste Hearing Touch Smell	Knowledge of the Perfection of Action

(Table adapted from Snodgrass, 2018).

The solar dynasty

In Chandra, 2008, we find discussed “*Borobudur as a symbol of the nation state of Indonesia*. The preponderance of the reliefs of the Gandavyuha and the clear implication of *Vairocana 'The Great Sun'* on three levels, invites an astounding comparison with the Nara Daibutsu or Colossus of Roshana (Skt. Rocana) dedicated in 752 by Emperor Shomu of Japan. In 743 Emperor Shomu issued a rescript ordering the construction of the colossus of Rocana, 16 metres in height, at the Todaiji monastery in his attempt to unify the nation in its awareness of power, as an "apt symbol of the emperor as the controlling head of the state" (Kobayashi 1975:22). It was to consolidate the sovereignty of the nation in a harmony of the emperor and his people on the deeper spiritual levels: "sagely within, kingly without." It was a Grand National Temple”. Let us also add from Chandra, 2008, that “*Both Rocana and Vairocana mean 'Sun'*. ... Thus Rocana of the Gandavyuha and Vairocana translated in Sino-Japanese as Dainichi "Great Sun" represent the Solar Dynasty, the Sailendras in the case of Indonesia” (Chandra, 2008).

“The Borobudur was topped by a stupa which was open when discovered. The opening was large enough for persons to enter this kutagara for worship. The first rays of the rising sun must have touched the Vairocana enshrined in the open kutagara, unfortunately closed in the reconstruction by Van Erp and now by the Unesco. Prof. Rolf A. Stein has clearly pointed out that the open stupa represents the vajradhatu-mandala (L'Annuaire du College de France 76.530). The Thousand Buddhas (504x2) are directional Buddhas well-known in the vajradhatu-mandala in Japan as the East Buddha, South Buddha, West Buddha and North Buddha” (Chandra, 2008).

Who Are the Six Buddhas of Borobudur?

This is the question posed by Caroline Gammon (2008). See please the references therein “A comparison of the images from the Van Erp survey and the Iconography of Nepalese Buddhism, shows the similarity of the Buddhas in the East with Aksobhya, South with Ratnasambhava, West with Amitabha, and those in the North with Amoghasiddhi. This was first suggested by Humbolt in 1836 and is the general scholastic opinion. The identity of the 64 Buddhas on the 5th gallery, and the 72 stupa Buddhas is more mysterious. They show respectively the vitarka mudra and what is considered to be a variation of the dharmacakra mudra. Toganoo Shoun in 1930 suggested the following identification after studying the Chinese commentaries on the proto-tantric Mahdvairocana sutra and Adhyardhasatika prajhaparamita. Professor van Lohuizen de Leeuw independently had the same idea in 1965. Their conclusion was:” (Gammon, 2008)

East	South	West	North	Centre	72 Stupas	Central Buddha
Aksobhya	Ratna-Sambhava	Amitabha	Amogha-siddhi	Samantabhadra-Vajradhara	Vairocana, 72 stupas = 72 dharmas	Aksobhya Vajrasattva

Adapted from Gammon, 2008.

“Soekmono thought the 5 dhyani Buddhas were emanations of the Adi-Buddha represented by the large central stupa. ... The Adi-Buddha is the primordial Buddha of the Indian Tathagatagarbha schools and later the Tibetan Nyingmapa and Jonangpa (Kalacakra based) schools” (Gammon, 2008).

	East	South	West	North	Zenith	72 Stupas
Dhyani Buddha	Aksobhya	Ratna-Sambhava	Amitabha	Amogha-siddhi	Vairocana	Vairocana
Bodhisattva	Vajrapani	Visvapani	Avalokita	Ratnapani	Samantabhadra	
Manusi Buddha	Kanakamuni	Maitreya	Sakyamuni	Kaysapa	Krakuchchanda	

Adapted from Gammon, 2008.

“Toganoo Shoun said that the Borobudur Buddhas are the 5 jinas of a Vajradhatu mandala, i.e. the 5 jinas with Vairocana in the centre ... Lama Gangchen like Soekmono (personal communication) said that the 5 'Supreme Healers' (jinas) of Borobudur are the Buddhas of a yogatantra mandala.” (Gammon, 2008).

East	South	West	North	Centre	72 Stupas
Aksobhya	Ratnasambhava	Amitabha	Amoghasiddhi	Vairocana	Vairocana

Adapted from Gammon, 2008.

Stupa or Mandala?

In “[The Incipient Tantrism of Borobudur](#)”, Debashish Banerji illustrates several questions regarding Borobudur. The purpose in his essay “is not to provide yet another totalizing interpretation of Borobudur, but to raise certain questions regarding the directions in the search for solutions so far followed, and to open up certain areas for further investigation. Principally the opinion over the purpose of the monument has divided itself into arguments for its interpretation as a stupa or a mandala.” (Debashish Banerji). See please the discussion in the Debashish Banerji’s essay.

About numerology, Debashish Banerji notes that “In a more interesting and bolder speculation, based not on the vajradhatu mandala, but on an equating of the three upper circles of Borobudur with the three mysteries of the Buddha, Body, Speech and Mind, constituting the dharmadhatu, Weyman explains the 72 Buddhas in dharmachakra mudra. Thus the four postures of the Body, three kinds of Speech and two varieties of Mind are each related to the eight spokes of the wheel of Law (dharmachakra) to obtain 32 outermost, 24 next and 16 innermost generations of the Buddha. Even more obvious than with the

deities, the match between the vajradhatu mandala and Borobudur in the matter of numerology, is extremely questionable; though here again, taken independently, a sense of symmetry and numerological significance seems to impress itself on us from Borobudur and cannot be easily dismissed.” (Debashish Banerji, mentioning Wayman 1981).

Borobudur Mandala

In the book by Giuseppe D’Acunto, entitled “Il disegno del Cosmo, L’architettura mandalica di Angkor Vat”, we can find a remarkable discussion of Borobudur. The book is in Italian. The proposed excerpts are translated in English.

“The temple that perhaps expresses spiritual and symbolic requests in a more eloquent and direct manner is Borobudur, that was built in 860 AD in Java according to a Buddhist matrix. Borobudur is a perfect example of a pyramid-shaped mountain stupa, as it fully embodies the Far Eastern cosmic symbolism. In the layout of Borobudur, we can find the Mandala Law. There is no monument in the world, Buddhist or otherwise, that can serve as a reference. With Borobudur, a new ‘art’ was born, and a new conception of ‘art’, which did not exist before, the result of Indian, Persian, Greek and even Babylonian influences. It was commissioned by the princes of the Sailendra dynasty, it was conceived by the sages of Tantric Buddhism, who guided the hand of the architect Gunadharma, it was designed by one of the most formidable teams of scientists (engineers, astronomers, mathematicians, physicists) in the history of humanity, it was built by ten thousand workers, artisans, sculptors and slaves over a period of almost a hundred of years. *The geographical position is not accidental: in the plains, there are two rivers that recall the sacred confluence of the Ganges and the Yamuna in India, and in the background, mountains rise that recall the profile of the Himalayas*” (D’Acunto, 2004).

Architect Gunadharma is also mentioned by Mark Long, in his "Architectural Survey of Borobudur's Summit", and in Miksic, 2012, where we find told that “according to legend, Borobudur was designed by a divine architect named Gunadharma, whose profile is said to be visible in the shape of the Menoreh Hills just south of Borobudur. Far from having been the work of a single designer, however, research shows that in fact Borobudur was remodeled four time within 50 years” (Miksic, 2012).

“Borobudur building consists of ten terraces, one for each stage of the spiritual process of elevation towards perfection, divided into three levels, corresponding to the three Buddhist spheres: the base represents life in the spirals of desire (kamadhatu), the five square terraces represent the progressive emancipation from senses (rupadhatu), while the three circular terraces become the ideal metaphor for the soul's progression towards nirvana (arupadhatu). At the top, the massive density of the previous levels suddenly stretches into open spaces, the complexity of the terraces evolves naturally into a simple tranquility ... The galleries of each terrace are accessed from the left to pay tribute to the gods, from the right for the demons; the galleries make up a five-kilometer labyrinth, along the walls of them are scattered 8,000 square meters of bas-reliefs, ... There are 1500 panels of the story of Buddha, and to them they must be added 1200 panels purely decorative. Altogether, they constitute a gigantic encyclopedia of Buddhist knowledge, embracing not only religion, but also history, art, philosophy, martial arts, agriculture, commerce, dance, even clothing. Even to the most profane eye, the jungle of mythological images immediately stands out, the crowd of divinities that crowd this universe where Buddha and Shiva are the same divinity” (D’Acunto, 2004)

The history of Borobudur

“The history of Borobudur has always been mysterious. Surprisingly there is no great temple or palace associated with it. It is usually assumed to have been built by Buddhist kings of the Sailendra dynasty, ‘the Lords of the Mountains’; but there is precious little evidence for this beyond one single surviving inscription. This is dated 842 and records a donation of land by a Sailendra princess to an unnamed

Buddhis sanctuary. Recently, however, archaeologists” have found close to the monument of Borobudur an inscription invoking Bodhisattva Vajrapani, “revealing a close link with the esoteric Vajarayana Buddhist movement ... It seems likely that the architect of Borobudur was one of the Javanese Tantric disciples, probably the monk known in the biographies under the Chinese version of his name, Bianhong” (Dalrymple, 2024, and references therein).

We will return to Borobudur, but now it is time to move from Java to Cambodia, to search number 108 in Khmer monuments

Phnom Bakheng, Cambodia

Let us consider the Angkor temples. Coordinates: 13.42418°N 103.85601°E, [Wikipedia](#), Location: Angkor, Siem Reap Province, Cambodia.

Wikipedia item tells that Phnom Bakheng is a Hindu temple. Let us stress that it was a Khmer “state temple” (we have further discussed this fact in [SSRN](#)). The temple was completed 889–910 AD. “Constructed more than two centuries before Angkor Wat, Phnom Bakheng was in its day the principal temple of the Angkor region, historians believe”, according to Wikipedia. “Phnom Bakheng is a symbolic representation of Mount Meru, home of the Hindu gods, a status emphasized by the temple's location atop a steep hill 65 m above the surrounding plain. The temple is built in a pyramid form of seven levels, representing the seven heavens [Higham, 2014]. At the top level, five sandstone sanctuaries, in various states of repair, stand in a quincunx pattern—one in the center and one at each corner of the level's square. *Originally, 108 small towers were arrayed around the temple at ground level and on various of its tiers*; most of them have collapsed [Rooney, 2002]” (Wikipedia and mentioned references).

“Jean Filliozat of the Ecole Francaise, a leading western authority on Indian cosmology and astronomy, interpreted the symbolism of the temple. ... Phnom Bakheng's total number of towers is also significant. The center one represents the axis of the world, and the 108 smaller ones represent the four lunar phases, each with 27 days. The seven levels of the monument represent the seven heavens, and each terrace contains 12 towers which represent the 12-year cycle of Jupiter. According to University of Chicago scholar Paul Wheatley, it is ‘an astronomical calendar in stone.’ ” (Wikipedia).

The web site <https://www.templemountains.org> is offering further information. And the specific link <https://www.templemountains.org/analysis-of-phnom-bakheng-s.html>, [archived](#).

“Yasovarman I built a new capital at Yasodharapura a few miles from the future sites of Angkor Wat and Angkor Thom, centered around his own state temple mountain located on the crest of an actual mountain, or at least a hill, rising 78m above the Angkorian plain named Phnom Bakheng (phnom is Khmer for hill.) ... Like the [Bakong](#), Yashovarman I’s pyramid had five-levels or terraces with a plinth on the uppermost one supporting a panchayatana or quincunx of shrines, surrounded on its terraces by sixty small shrines and forty-four medium-sized ones around its base. Phnom Bakheng thus turns an actual mountain into the cella or base of a five-tier man-made “temple mountain” which acts as its shikhara, with **108** shrines, each itself an aedicule of a temple mountain, strung around these five levels like the talas or haras of a Dravida vimana. Of all the temple mountains the Khmer built, *Phnom Bakheng seems most cognizant of its possible Javanese precedent, Borobudur, in the multiple small, identical shrines lining its five terraces which are, however*, too narrow to allow circumambulation, thus precluding the need for mural bas reliefs and the didactic purpose of its putative original. The forty-four large shrines surrounding the pyramid’s base also recall the phalanx of 224 pevara or guardian candi or small shrines standing watch at Candi Siwa at Roro Jonggrang (Prambanan,) Java. Nonetheless, the Bakheng’s 108 shrines would be an impressive number of aedicules on the shikhara of all but the most ambitious Indonesian and Indian temples.” (templemountains.org).

The number 108 is also mentioned in Ching et al., 2017, p. 301 (here the link to [Google Books](#)): “On the top of this hill, Yasovarman built his primary royal temple, Yasodharesvara, known today as Phnom Bakheng. Phnom Bakheng sits on a platform, created through cut and fill, at the summit of the hill. Its five terraces, a man-made mountain on top of the natural mountain, culminate in a plateau with four shrines around a central Shiva shrine. Another 103 shrines are distributed geometrically on the terraces, bringing the total to 108, an auspicious number by Hindu astrology. A sophisticated system of numerology – number of towers, steps, and ascending hierarchy of sculptural groups – reinforced the temple’s association with Shiva. As to Bakong, Phnom Bakheng was surrounded by a moat, and the terracing creates a spherical profile. From the summit, the temple affords expansive views, in particular towards the mountains in the north. Some of them seem to have the outline of Naga to protect and define the vast flood plain.”

“The number 108 is highly important in Hinduism. All Hindu eras, or yugas, are comprised of large numbers divisible by 108, while mantras are often repeated 108 times. The number is considered as a ‘building block’ of the universe. ... At Angkor, the early mountain temple of Phnom Bakheng had its central sanctuary surrounded by 108 smaller ones” (<https://sailingstonetravel.com/decoding-the-symbolism-of-angkor/>).

“In Hindu/Buddhist beliefs, there are 108 feelings, 108 earthly desires, 108 human delusions or forms of ignorance, 108 earthly temptations, humans tell 108 lies, 108 dance poses (karanas) in the Natya Shastra, 108 music talas and ragas, 108 Hindu deities, 108 gopis in Gaudiya Vaishnavism, 108 Upanishads, 108 qualities of praiseworthy souls, 108 Jain virtues, 108 paths to Gods.” (Agarwal, 2013). We can find also told by Agarwal that there are 19 constellations and 9 planets, so $12 \times 9 = 108$. Rama has been called by 108 different names.

When we search for numbers 108, or 72, in architecture, we are making ‘numerology’. Is it a ‘pseudoscience’? Is this numerology a ‘pseudo-scientific way of reasoning’? [T. Darvill](#), in his response to two archaeoastronomer, was right telling that numerology “is regularly observed amongst non-Western societies”.

Fig. 6: Statues along the South Gate bridge, Angkor Thom. Photograph Courtesy Colin W. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported license.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Angkor_Thom#/media/File:Angkor_Thom_South_Gate,_Angkor_-_panoramio.jpg

Angkor Thom

The causeway to the South Gate, which is leading to Angkor Thom, has **108 statues, 54 gods and 54 demons**. These 108 statues are guarding the entrance. We can easily follow this causeway on the bridge flanked by statues by means of Google Earth Street View. The iconography is inspired by the epic on the Churning of the Ocean of Milk. The statues are positioned on opposite sides according to good and evil.

Churning of the Ocean of Milk

‘The Churning of the Ocean of Milk’ was a favorite story of many Khmer artists and kings. It begins with the devas, or gods, being cursed by a powerful sage, leaving them as easy targets for their arch-rivals, the asuras ... They soon learned, however, that amrita, or the elixir of immortality, lie at the bottom of a milky ocean. As the ocean needed to be churned to obtain it, the devas and asuras had no choice but to cooperate with each other to get it out. The ocean was so big that the peak of Mt. Mandara was used as the churning rod. For stabilization, Vishnu transformed himself into a turtle named Kurma, on top of whom the peak was placed. And to spin the mountain peak, the devas and asuras used the naga king Vasuki as a churning rope. He wrapped himself around the peak as the two teams each took one side of his long body and began to pull. As they started to churn, ...” sailingstonetravel.com “The story also contains significant numerological symbolism. The two teams consisted of 54 devas and 54 asuras. The number 108 is highly important in Hinduism. All Hindu eras, or yugas, are comprised of large numbers divisible by 108, while mantras are often repeated 108 times. The number is considered as a ‘building block’ of the universe. ... At Angkor, the early mountain temple of Phnom Bakheng had its central sanctuary surrounded by 108 smaller ones.”

Fig7: Large Deva Churning the Sea of Milk, Angkor Wat . “This is the middle of three large devas that participate in the churning. Its identification is unknown; Brahma, Shiva, and Vishnu have all been proposed.” Photograph and description by Michael Gunther. Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license. [Large Deva Churning the Sea of Milk Angkor Wat](http://Large%20Deva%20Churning%20the%20Sea%20of%20Milk%20Angkor%20Wat)

*Fig. 8 Bayon temple. Photograph by Sasha India, CC BY 2.0,
[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bayon#/media/File:Bayon_0759_\(27773814040\).jpg](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bayon#/media/File:Bayon_0759_(27773814040).jpg)*

1 (unit) 0 (nothingness) 8 (infinity), that is, further numerology

Here some passages, translated from Italian, of ["Cambogia, dove i numeri sono angeli"](#), Odifreddi, 2014. "In the temple of Angkor, the bas-reliefs tell the birth of life. The spirits and demons are 108: 1 (unity), 0 (nothingness), 8 (infinity). ... But what remains on site is still one of the wonders of the world, and its crown jewels are the sacred temple of Angkor Wat, the profane mound of the Bayon, and the natural memorial of Ta Prohm. The first is certainly the symbolic attraction of the town, ... It was built around 1100 as a huge mandala with concentric rectangles; each perimeter of the rectangles corresponds to an ascent of physical and spiritual level. And the passage from one level to another symbolizes the ascent to the mythical Mount Meru with the five peaks, that Hindus and Buddhists consider the center of the world. The galleries surrounding the various levels and the central temple with five towers, are dotted with votive chapels of the two religions and covered with bas-reliefs, representing scenes from the Mahabharata and the Ramayana. The most famous is the spectacular, fifty-meter-long one, Churning of the Ocean of Milk; 108 angels (devas) and demons (asuras) pull a giant snake (naga) wrapped around a mountain used as a whisk for a thousand of years, to produce the nectar of immortality. ... 108 is the magic number of Hindus and Buddhists, because through its digits it represents the union of unity (1), nothingness (0) and infinity (8). Number 108 is also found in the rosary beads, and in the 54 angels and 54 demons that line the access bridges to the second wonder of Angkor: the Bayon, the symbolic and planimetric center of the old capital Angkor Thom. The building is one of the oldest examples of fractal architecture, in which the structure of the whole is reflected in the structure of the parts, suggesting an infinite regression. Each of the 54 towers of the complex possesses on each of the four sides an image of King Jayavarman VII, who built it around 1200. And the 216 images observe pilgrims and tourists from all sides, giving no respite to them. This does not prevent the mathematician from observing, in some chapels, the phallic lingam of Shiva in a three-stage version: with a square section at the bottom,

octagonal in the center and circular at the top. Symbolically, the three parts represent the trinity (trimurti) of Brahma, Vishnu and Shiva. Mathematically, they are reminiscent of the Indian approximation of 3.11 to the value of pi, obtained by noting that if you cut the corners of a square, you get a non-regular octagon almost equivalent to the inscribed circle” (Odifreddi, 2014).

Numerology from Barnhart and Powell

Here some *Numerology* by [Barnhart and Powell, 2015](#). “ On the back (east) side of Angkor Wat’s main enclosure the wall is carved with a long scene of the mythic churning of the sea of milk. Pulling the giant body of the snake king Naga back and forth, devas and asuras (gods and demons) play a tug of war that churns the sea into a froth that will release the elixir of immortality. While this scene is all over Angkor, *this portrayal is unique in that it has 89 devas and 91 asuras doing the pulling*”. That is, Barnhart and Powell are stressing that the ‘Churning of the Sea of Milk’ is present many times in Angkor, but that there is a peculiar representation of it, peculiar for the numbers of gods and demons. “Eleanor Mannikka (1996) recognized this as the number of days between equinoxes and solstices. Another unique feature of this churning depiction is that [it has] notably larger devas [see the figure in Barnhart and Powell]. At number 29 on the deva side and 30 on the asura side are the first two larger figures. If the total number of pullers represents a count of days between solar stations, it’s possible these two positions represent one moon phase to either side of the central figure, Vishnu. Then at 57 and 59 respectively to either side are the other two larger figures. Adding these two numbers up, we get a total of 116, just off the 114 days *between Angkor’s two zenith passage dates*. If Mannikka’s identification of equinox and solstice numerology here is correct, then these two-figures positions are most logically explained as the zenith passage days of August 17 and April 25. However, this hypothesis would call for a change to Mannikka’s theory that the central figure of Vishnu sits at equinox. Instead, the date would be the June 21 summer solstice, with 57 days before being Angkor’s first zenith passage on April 25th and 59 days later being August 19th, just two days off Angkor’s second annual zenith passage. Though Mannikka prefers to interpret Vishnu as sitting in the position of equinox, her photos of dawn at summer solstice better support our hypothesis. Figure 18 [in Barnhart and Powell, 2015] shows Mannikka’s photo of the churning scene’s pivot point at one hour after actual sun rise. ...” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015).

“This would not be the only example of zenith passage numerology in Angkor. Mark Long of Borobudur TV and Caesar Voûte have suggested another possible numerological reference to zenith passage at the gates of Angkor Thom. Quoting the account of Chinese trader Zhou Daguan, Long states that a fifth, golden head once stood atop the four faced head above each of Angkor Thom’s five gates. Each gate was reached by a bridge over the moat surrounding the city. Each bridge was lined with 108 supernaturals pulling the body of the snake (Figure 19 [of Barnhart and Powell]), 54 devas on one side and 54 asuras on the other. Long suggested that $54 + 5 + 54 = 113$, the number of days between Angkor’s two zenith passages. Further, they hypothesize that the five heads all on the gate tower represent how the Sun hangs at a single horizon position at summer solstice, the mid-way point between zenith passages.” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015).

We have seen two sites, Borobudur and Angkor, where the number 108 is present in the architecture. We have also considered the 72 statues inside the stupas at the top platform of Borobudur. That is, we have considered numerology linked to architecture. As previously told, in the case of number 72, we considered in 2017, a possible application to calendar in Java. Java is in the tropical zone, and then we assumed a role of the zenith passage of the sun, in subdividing the years in four parts, determined by the two zenith passages and the solstice of December. We have seen that at Borobudur the Buddha of the zenith is that at the top of the monument. Then, let us discuss the zenithal sun at Angkor and Borobudur.

The zenith passage of the sun at Angkor and Borobudur

When I wrote about the zenith passage of the sun at the [Sewu temple](#) and [Borobudur, Prambanan and Sewu temples](#), I considered number 72 as the number of days passing from the zenith passage of October 12 to December solstice, and from December solstice to the zenith passage on the end of February (or first of March). In total, $2 \times 72 - 1 = 143$. But we could count the days from February/March to October, “with June solstice right in between”, obtaining 222 days. This different manner of counting the days *has been proposed too, and before my discussion in 2017*. Therefore, it is *fundamental to me* to carefully report this proposal that we can find in the Barnhart and Powell discussion, 2015, of zenith passage of the sun. We will find the number of 224 days between the two zenith passages over the Prambanan temple in Java. However, the focus of Barnhart and Powell is Angkor, Cambodia, as we have seen before. Here again the [link](#) to the discussion by Barnhart and Powell.

“Numerology can sometimes indicate recognition of specific celestial cycles. As a collection of 365 objects or architectural features would symbolize the days of a solar year, zenith passages at specific latitudes could be indicated by the number of days in between them. In the case of Angkor, that number would be 114” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015).

Then Barnhart and Powell report a discovery at Angkor. “Though it is not apparent from the outside, each one of the beehive shaped temples of Angkor are hollow on the inside. Walking in and looking straight up, the roof is open all the way up to the top and that top has a hole where the sun shines in. We were told by the temple attendants that the holes on top of the roofs were there because the capstones had all been knocked off by erosion or more commonly by looters searching for jewels. Finding these fallen capstones among the rubble around the temples was our first surprising clue. Most capstones were beautifully carved as lotus flowers, and all had a hollow tube running down their axes. Each had a very straight, long tube that would have let only true zenith passage sun light down into the temples (Figures 3a-1). Whether or not this was their intention, functionally this makes every single temple of this kind at Angkor a zenith tube.” That is, at Angkor, people used the zenith tubes to observe the zenithal passage of the sun.

Lowering their eyes, Barnhart and Powell these temples, saw “what this zenith passage light would hit. The most common object found there was a carved stone linga. Lined up exactly in the center of the chamber, these lingas, ... would indeed function as gnomons, albeit surprising inside a temple!”. See [Figure 4 in Barnhart and Powell](#) of the zenithal light falling on the linga.

See please the whole article by Barnhart and Powell to appreciate their archaeoastronomical work, *regarding the alignments of the monuments with the rising of the zenithal sun. Indeed, Barnhart and Powell made archaeoastronomy.*

As already said, in their article, we find also the Ocean of Milk. And we find Prambanan in Java too.

“Perhaps due to the violent events on Southeast Asia’s mainland over the last few decades, a literature search turned up virtually no studies of ancient Khmer astronomy. However, Mark Long and Ceasar Voûte have discovered some compelling evidence in ancient Java (Long 2002). First, Long has presented convincing evidence of zenith passage numerology encoded in the Loro Jonggrang temple complex at Prambanan, located in central Java just east of the modern city of Yogyakarta ($7^{\circ}45'21''$ S, $110^{\circ}29'21''$ E). The complex is clearly Hindu inspired, with three tall shrines at its center dedicated to Brahma (south), Shiva (center), and Vishnu (north). Around that central yard is Yard II, containing 224 perwara temples [ancillary temples]. As the two zenith passages for this latitude ($7^{\circ}45'S$) occur on February 26th and October 9th, the distance between these two events, with June solstice right in between, is 224 days. Long suggests that these 224 temples denote a recognition of zenith passage *and the authors of this paper [that is, Barnhart and Powell] agree*. What Long did not recognize (at least in print) was another element of the Loro Jonggrang complex that strengthens his hypothesis. The outermost walls of the complex, enclosing Yard I, are at an odd angle as compared to the inner yards which follow the standard Hindu inspired pattern of cardinal direction alignment. Measuring the angle

of that outer compound, we find an angle of 8° south of east, the very same azimuth as zenith passage sunrise at Prambanan” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015).

To understand ancient Mayan society, we should go to Bali

“Whatever the case, Long mentions in a personal communication that a few years Mayan scholar Coe (author of *Breaking the Maya Code*) said in an interview that if we want to understand ancient Mayan society we should go to Bali, and proposed that a Mayan scholar conference be held in Bali for this purpose. Of course, Coe was not suggesting direct contact, but rather that the two societies were similar in many respects, thus confirming broadly the possibility of a Southeast Asian cultural influence brought about through Malaysian sailors” (Amon, 2005).

“Coe’s comments prompted a further investigation of the topic by Mark Long, who confirms that the Balinese continue *to use a dual calendar system* that is in some respects similar to the ancient Maya system, including a divinatory almanac (the Maya almanac being 260 days, the Balinese Pawukon being 210 days). He found that some Meso-American archaeologists believe that the Mayan almanac originated through astronomical observations around the latitude of Copan, where the number of days between the two sun zenith events each year equals the number of days in the Mayan almanac.” (Amon, 2009). See please Amon, 2005, and references therein.

“The Balinese observe (besides the Gregorian calendar) two completely different and not synchronized calendars: The Balinese pawukon calendar, a numeric calendar of 210 days per year; The Balinese saka calendar, a lunisolar calendar starting every Nyepi” ([Wikipedia](#)).

Numerology, Aveni, 2011

Before discussing, for comparison, the 260-day Mayan calendar, let us consider Aveni, 2011. “One tends to think of the study of pure number as an esoteric pursuit. But for the ancient Maya, particularly when it came to temporal matters, numbers were more than mere devices to tally units of time. In stark contrast to the Western calendar, in the Maya realm of timekeeping the duration between ritual events seems to have mattered as much as the times when the events themselves occurred. ... Among these motives were the need to: a) arrive at or avoid particular lucky or unlucky days; b) accommodate changing seasonal or other astronomical events; and c) set up numerological mirror symmetries, a characteristic that resonates with the Pythagorean philosophy of number” (Aveni, 2011).

“A seasonal calendar in use in Java in the nineteenth century consisted of the following month lengths (Crawfurd 1867): 41 23 24 24 26 41/ 41 26 25 25 23 41. Counted from the middle, the delineation of the day count in the second half of the year is almost a mirror image of that in the first half (read backward and forward from the ‘/’). The intervals were determined by the change in the position of the noon-time shadow cast by a vertical gnomon that measured equal spatial lengths (rather than equal time intervals) on a dial plate. The resulting 12 months are unequal because the noonday sun advances from day to day up and down the meridian more slowly near the solstices than near the equinoxes. *The pivot point in the symmetrical sequence is marked by the day of the passage of the sun through the zenith of the 7°N latitude location of the observer.* Dutch anthropologists who later investigated this unusual way of partitioning the year learned that the lengths of the months, so determined, were then adjusted slightly to accommodate agricultural timings related to the rice-planting schedule in the Javanese calendar (Maass 1924)” (Aveni, 2011).

“In the example of the Javanese calendar, a rational, observationally based motive underlies the mirror calendar phenomenon” (Aveni, 2011).

The Planetarium and the Plough

That is, *Interpreting Star Calendars of Rural Java*. Ammarell, G. (1996). “In contrast to the numerological calendar, the annual migrations across the celestial sphere of the Sun and two groups of stars represent three of the many natural cycles observed by Javanese rice farmers. The place of these cycles in the reckoning of their agricultural calendar and certain aspects of the [Ammarell’s] reconstruction of that calendar, using a planetarium star projector,” is the subject of Ammarell, 1996.

From Ammarell and Tsing, 2015. “In many parts of Indonesia, people use their knowledge of the movements of the stars and patterns of stars, or “asterisms”, as markers for annual seasonal changes. In a wide variety of ecological regimes— irrigated and rain-fed wet-rice agriculture, non-irrigated shifting cultivation, and even the palm and corn cultivation systems of the drier eastern islands— the annual movements of stars have been used to bring together cultivation calendars and seasonal environments changes, particularly rain fall changes. Historically, the Javanese probably developed one of the most elaborated correlations between the movement of stars and the cultivation cycle for wet rice in the region: The end of one agricultural cycle and the beginning of the new one was marked with observations of the heliacal rising of the Pleiades and then Orion at dawn in June; the sowing of rice seed was correlated with the appearance of these asterisms in the evening in November and December; the transplanting of rice was expected to be finished before the evening heliacal culmination of the Pleiades in late January; and the ending of the harvest season was noted to correlate with the heliacal setting of Orion at dusk and with the appearance of the Pleiades in the east just before dawn ... Javanese farmers seem to have observed the full annual cycle of changes in the nightly positions of these stars, and they used their knowledge of the regularity of these movements to time particular stages of cultivation and discuss agricultural regularities over time in a discourse on recurrent annual seasons. Other Indonesian have marked the movements of these and other stars, But, unlike the Javanese, both groups pay little attention to stellar movements for the rest of the agricultural year” (Ammarell and Tsing, 2015).

260-day calendar

Here is what Earle and Snow, 1983, told us about the origin of the Maya 260-day calendar. “One of the most important calendrical system is the 260-day cycle, often referred to as the “sacred almanac” or “tzolkin” by scholars. It is widespread and is at once perhaps the most ancient and most durable component of Mesoamerican calendars. It still survives in many places. Despite its antiquity and importance in the generation of the 52-year cycle, there is little consensus regarding the origin. ... A relatively recent published debate of the issue began with Malmstrom’s (1973) revival of the hypothesis that the 260-day cycle originates near the latitude of 15°N, where the sun passes its zenith at alternating intervals of approximately 260 and 105 days. Copan lies at about this latitude, but the site’s origin postdates the origin of the sacred almanac, and Malmstrom reasonably suggests that Copan was more likely to have been built where it was because of the sacred almanac than the other way around. Nevertheless, he like the idea of tying the 260-day calendar to the period of the zenithal sun positions, and has searched for sites that are both early enough and located near enough to the line of 15°N latitude to qualify as the birth place of the sacred almanac. He settles on Izapan, even though he has no calendric evidence from the site to back up his claim” (Earle and Snow, 1982, mentioning Malmstrom, 1973).

“The sacred 260-day Mesoamerican calendar probably originated near a latitude of 15°N, where there is a 260-day interval between transits of the zenithal sun. Archeological and faunal evidence favors an origin in the Pacific lowlands rather than in the highlands near Copán, Honduras, although Copán, which is located at the 15th parallel of latitude, later became the principal Mayan astronomical center” (Malmstrom, 1973).

“The most serious objection to explaining the origin of the sacred almanac in terms of the interval between zenithal sun positions has been forcefully expressed by Thompson (3, pp.98-99). Although

there is a 260-day interval between the autumn and spring zenithal transits of the sun (within the critical latitudinal band), there is a complementary 105-day interval between the spring and autumn positions. The sacred almanac, on the other hand, ran continuously; ... It is extremely unlikely that the 260-day cycle could have been based upon any natural phenomenon that was not continuously repetitive and that was not observable in the greater part of the area in which the sacred almanac was in use. The nature of the 260-day cycle does not force the conclusion that it was based upon a natural phenomenon” (Henderson, 1974, and references therein).

“The two most widely used calendars in pre-Columbian Mesoamerica were the 260-day Tzolk’in and the 365-day Haab’. The equivalent Aztec calendars are known in Nahuatl as the Tonalpohualli and Xihpohualli, respectively. The combination of a Haab’ and a Tzolk’in date identifies a day in a combination which does not occur again for 18,980 days (52 Haab’ cycles of 365 days equals 73 Tzolk’in cycles of 260 days, approximately 52 years), a period known as the Calendar Round. To identify days over periods longer than this, Mesoamericans used the Long Count calendar” ([Wikipedia](#)).

Had the Haab’ calendar a *leap year*? Let us read the discussion held by J. Foster for [Quora](#). “The Maya had a number of different time cycles, including what is called the Haab or “Civil Year’. It was 365 days long, so was a Vague Tropical Year. And the Maya were aware that the Tropical Year was actually a little longer than 365 days. They did not however insert an intercalary day. They did maintain a “correction factor” though and on some of their stele, or ‘monuments’, put in along with other cycle dates, the Haab or Vague Tropical Year correction.” (Foster, in Quora).

We could ask ourselves: was the observation of the zenith passage of the sun a manner to maintain the “Civil Year” in agreement with seasons? And this is proper for Maya lands, Java and Cambogia too.

Building orientations and zenith-sighting tube

“Building orientations can stand as meridians, permanent markers of daily zenith passage. For example, the west walls of building can be oriented north-south such that they are in shade in the morning and then are relatively abruptly illuminated in midday as the sun passes the zenith (e.g. Malmström, 1997). Such constructions and their *hierophanies* might provide a way of marking the start of the day (or a season, or a new year), or, *if somehow used* as a basis for calibrating midnight, they might mark the start of a new day in the middle of the night, as Westerners do at present. Certain distinctive structural features at sites throughout Mesoamerica seem to have functioned in solar observations and/or day counts. For example, a “*zenith-sighting tube*” was built as a vertical tunnel into the stairway of Structure P at Monte Albán, in Oaxaca (Aveni, 2001). Two similar tubes were built into a cave at Xochicalco, one of which, tellingly, illuminates the cave for 102 days (Aveni, 2001; Manzanilla, 2000). Excavations in the Maya lowlands have led to discovery of the possible location of a gnomon: the shadow of a post set into a posthole in the center of a structure fell on an embedded stone in a platform to the southwest at the summer solstice sunrise (Zaro and Lohse, 2005).” (Prudence M. Rice, 2009)

For the zenith passage at Monte Albán, see please [Fig.1 in Šprajc, 2018](#). Caption tells “The Sun’s rays on a zenith passage day falling into the chamber of Structure P at Monte Albán, Oaxaca, Mexico (photograph by I. Šprajc)”.

The Mayan solar Zenith

The dates for sowing and harvesting were, and still are, fixed by the Maya at the two annual zenith passage days of the sun, when the sun is directly overhead, when a gnomon cast no shadow at noon. At some Mesoamerican sites, such as Xochicalco and Monte Alban, there are buildings in which a zenith tube projects a vertical sunbeam onto the floor at midday. In the Yucatan, bottle-shaped underground chambers called chultunes may have served for the same purposes. There are two seasons – rainy and dry, starting in April/May and November. The onset of the rainy season coincides with the first zenith

passage in May for much of the Maya area, and maize (corn) is planted shortly after. At the second solar passage a second maize crop is planted. At higher altitudes, maize and beans are planted in March and harvested 260 days later in December. The solar nadir dates ... Zenith tubes may also have been used to observe the zenith passage of important constellations” (Stray, 2007).

Zenith tubes at Angkor Wat

I published, on Wednesday 13th April 2016, in [Philica](#) an article entitled The Zenith Passage of the Sun and its role in the Planning of Architectures. [Philica was an instant publishing journal](#), that is, the text was freely available for everyone immediately after uploaded. I told the following, after a discussion of the zenith passage of the sun in Americas.

The zenith passage was important for the people of Asia. And in fact, in Sparavigna, 2013, we have shown that the archaeological complex of Sigiriya, the Lion Rock, in Sri Lanka has its axis oriented to the sunset on days of zenith passage of the sun. Let us also consider the very important Buddhist religious center of Sanchi, which has interesting astronomical orientations as discussed by N. Kameswara Rao; it possesses a particular alignment of stupas with the sunset direction on the summer solstice. Since Sanchi latitude is close to the Tropic of Cancer, we have also that, on this day, the noon altitude is about 90 degrees. Therefore, the alignment of stupas is also giving the sunset direction of the day of the zenithal sun (Sparavigna, 2015).

The first written mention of zenith passage in Indian literature comes from Varahamihira in the 6th century (Barnhart & Powell; Sastry & Kuppanna,1993), who noted that in the kingdom of Avanti the day of summer solstice and zenith passage were the same (the Avanti Kingdom of ancient India was described in the Mahabharata epic). He further discussed that north of Avanti no zenith passage occurs. Varahamihira wrote these observations when he was in the ancient city of Ujjain, located at latitude of 23° 10' 12" N (Barnhart & Powell).

As observed Barnhart and Powell, the ancient India had a “prime meridian” and a north-south “zero” line of latitude crossing at Ujjain and running straight down to the island of Lanka. The southern part of India is in the tropical zone such as another part of Southeast Asia, like the Indochina. The article by Barnhart and Powell [is a very interesting paper](#), discussing the importance of zenith passage of the sun in the architecture of the temples at Angkor Wat, Cambodia. *Edwin Barnhart and Christopher Powell, University of Texas, Austin, in August of 2010 and 2011 investigated the importance of the zenith passage of the Sun for ancient Khmer culture.* They concluded the research with a positive answer. "From architectural features and orientations to art panels and monuments, the evidence that zenith passage was recognized permeates the entire city". According to Barnhart and Powell, their idea "to search for evidence of zenith passage at Angkor" was inspired by prior research in Mesoamerica. In their work, besides discussing the discoveries at Angkor, the authors are proposing that the Hindu culture was also including some references to the zenith passage of the sun.

As previously told, Barnhart and Powell have discovered that Angkor temples had vertical zenith sighting tubes too. “Whether or not this was their intention, functionally this makes every single temple of this kind at Angkor a zenith tube” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015). Besides the temples which are beautiful artificial caves for the zenithal sun, the authors have observed that this architectural complex possesses also alignments to mark the zenith passage at Angkor Wat.

And in Barnhart and Powell, we can find a discussion about numerology.

About the use of the zenith tube, someone could say that is better to use a vertical pole; however the discussion by Barnhart and Powell, 2015, clarify this point: “1) Gnomons are the most basic tools one can build to observe a zenith passage. A straight, plumb stick or post in the ground can be watched for the day during which it casts no shadow at noon. Looking at photos of Angkor prior to our visit, lingas and perhaps temple tops seemed possible gnomon candidates. 2) Zenith sighting tubes are the most

exacting and accurate way to determine the days of zenith passage. While the absence of shadows off a gnomon can be hard to observe at just the right day and moment, a straight vertical tube leading from the open sky into a dark chamber will produce an unmistakably powerful beam of light only on the day of zenith passage. The best, most accurate tubes are long and narrow. In Mesoamerica zenith sighting tubes have been found at Monte Alban, Xochicalco, and Teotihuacan. Could such tubes exist at Angkor? A picture looking up at a hole in the roof of the library south-east of Prasat Pram gave us hope” (Barnhart and Powell, 2015).

I told about pre-Columbian Mesoamerica in my [Philica](#). “The people of preColumbian Mexico had a specific “astronomical instrument” to observe this passage: a vertical zenith sighting tube inserted in the vault of an underground structure. One of these instruments is at observatory of Xochicalco, in the Mexican state of Morelos. The image in the Figure 1 illustrates how it can look like the beam of light passing through the ceiling of the artificial cave of Xochicalco”. In fact, we have seen in the previously given references that there is also the site at Monte Albán (see again the picture in [Fig.1 in Šprajc, 2018](#)). “A vertical opening produces in a dark chamber a perfectly perpendicular beam of light when the sun is at the local zenith. Besides the cave, at Xochicalco there is a white stone pillar in the ceremonial area that could have been used to observe the shadow disappearing at the zenith passage of the sun (Figure 2). For Meso- and South America, several researchers have recognized and evidenced the importance of the zenith passage” (Sparavigna, 2016, and references therein). And “it is stressed that, among the ancient civilizations that recognized the zenith passage, we have also those of the Andean people of Peru, that incorporated it into their cosmology. The Andean people used pillars, such as the Chankillo Towers, as solar observations and for their calendars” (Sparavigna, 2016, and references therein).

About the cave let us add Lebeuf, 2015, and the “Cave of the Astronomers at [Xochicalco](#)”. “The chimney built in the roof of the *artificial large cave* at Xochicalco, known as “Cave of the astronomers”, has been interpreted as a solar zenithal observation tube. Nevertheless, different elements and especially the latitude of the site itself led the author to present a lunar hypothesis. Precise measurements of the impact of light inside the cave show the degree of precision that can be obtained in this camera obscura” (Lebeuf, 2015). *Let us return to Angkor Wat.*

Archaeoastronomy of Khmer architectures

Let us consider again the book written by D’Acunto (see please references therein).

“The idea of assimilating the temple to a microcosm, is common to many social and religious systems of our planet; although distant both from a temporal and geographical point of view, these systems have been able to devise a vast symbolic set of codes for their architectural expression. In particular, regarding the experience of Khmer architecture in Angkor, numerous studies have shown that even in this case the temples were built in perfect adherence to certain cosmological and astronomical principles, through two paths. One path was of purely symbolic nature, thanks to which the cosmos is embodied in the stones of the temples of Angkor through precise specific architectural forms and measurements. The other path was of a scientific nature, providing, to the construction of the sacred buildings, even the role of real astronomical observatories, suitable for contemplating celestial phenomena, also considered as divine manifestations” (D’Acunto, 2004).

“Khmer people had reached around the year 1000 good knowledge in the astronomical field: the Chinese chronicler Chou Ta-Kuan, who spent a year in Angkor towards the end of the fourteenth century, states in his travel diary that that country was well supplied with “... men who understand astronomy well and can calculate eclipses of the sun and moon”. From another literary source we learn that astronomy was called 'sacred science' at Angkor and was held in such high esteem that the destruction of astronomical manuscripts and documents was considered a crime punishable by 'eternal damnation' ”(D’Acunto, 2004).

According to D'Acunto, "George Coedes considered the Angkor temples as 'stone representations of the great myths of Hindu cosmology'. The purpose of this system was to reproduce on earth an earthly model of all or part of the celestial world, thus ensuring an intimate harmony between the two worlds without which humanity could not prosper. According to the Hindu system of thought, the universe consists of seven island-continent surrounded by seven seas. Jambu-dwipa (the world) is the innermost of these; in the center of this continent rises the golden mountain Meru, which rises 84,000 leagues above the earth; Meru is dotted with four other mountains, each of which is 10,000 leagues high, one of which is Mandera. This first description is necessary to clarify how certain typological choices of Angkor temples are inextricably linked to factors of a symbolic order, rather than being of a functional type; in particular, the classic arrangement of the towers according to the motif defined as a 'quincunx' takes on the value of a terrestrial copy of Mount Meru, imagined with five peaks, and therefore an architectural metaphor of the universe" (D'Acunto, 2004).

"Having embodied the idea of the universe, in a precise architectural typology, was only the prelude to a long series of cosmological and astronomical considerations to be transferred to the microcosm of the Khmer temple: one of these certainly concerns its orientation with respect to the cardinal directions which, although always dictated by mystical needs, offers, from a methodological point of view, some considerable ideas for scientific considerations. Generally, many sacred buildings in Angkor have the main entrance facing east, the longitudinal axis following an east-west alignment, reflecting the winter solar cycle. However, some temples, no less important, depart from this rule: and it is precisely the case of Angkor Wat which turns the main front towards the west: this unusual choice that orients the temple towards sunset seems to refer to the idea of death, an idea therefore closely linked to the final destination of the monument, that of a funeral mausoleum for the sovereign" (D'Acunto, 2004).

"In particular, in the temple of Angkor Wat, the long east-west axis is arranged perfectly in line with sunset and sunrise on equinoxes, so that on the day of the spring equinox, 'an observer standing at the southern edge of the first projection on the causeway (just in front of the eastern entrance gate) can see the sun rising directly on the top of the central tower of Angkor Wat. Three days later, the sun can be seen rising exactly over the top of the central tower from the center of the causeway, just in front of the western entrance gate'. This precise observation of the sun at the vernal equinox is extremely important (D'Acunto, quoting Stencel et al., 1976). This dual observation system, capable of allowing the contemplation of the same alignment from two different positions over the course of three days, is the result of a refined astronomical calculation that imposes an intentional shift of the axis of the temple of Angkor Wat of 0.75 degrees east to south and 0.75 degrees west to north, so as to interact with the general layout of the temple and thus provide visitors with a three-days' notice of equinox" (D'Acunto, 2004).

"The temple itself is significantly linked to the earth and sky by indicators of other fundamental astronomical moments of the year. For example, as reported by the article in journal Science, it is interesting to note that two solstitial alignments can be detected from the entrance gate of Angkor Wat. These two alignments (added to the two equinoctial alignments already established) mean that the entire solar year was divided into its four fundamental sections (equinoxes and solstices) by alignments just within Angkor Wat" (D'Acunto, 2004).

"Since the Cambodian calendar was based on lunar and solar cycles, this precise observation of the sun at the spring equinox is extremely important. The spring equinox marks the beginning of the sun's annual journey, regardless of the exact date of the lunar-solar new year. Whether this crucial alignment was intended for practical observation or religious orientation, or both, is impossible to determine" (Stencel et al., 1976).

Fig.9: “Equinox sunrise on Angkor Wat in 2012”, Courtesy សុខគឹមហេង, [Wikipedia](#)

“It is interesting to note that there are also two solstitial alignments from the western entrance gate of Angkor Wat. These two added alignments mean that the entire solar year was divided into four major sections by alignments from just inside the entrance of Angkor Wat. From this western vantage point, the sun rises over Phnom Bok on the day of the summer solstice (6,7). Phnom Bok is a major hill on the plain of Angkor and is located 17.4 kilometers northeast of Angkor Wat. The western entrance gate of the temple also has a winter solstice alignment with the temple of Prasat Kuk Bangro, 5,5 kilometers to the southeast (8)” (Stencel et al., 1976). In the Notes (6) and (7), we find: in (6) it is mentioned P. Paris, Bull. Ec. Fr. Extr. Orient 41, 323 (1941), and in (7), “this alignment includes the eastern entrance of Banteay Kdei, constructed at the end of the 12th century. Phnom Bok rises 160 m from ground level. An observer would have to be high up on the tower in order to observe the sun rise over Phnom Bok on the summer solstice day. Alignment is very important, whether actual observations took place or not” (Stencel et al., 1976).

“Like most *celestial cities*, Angkor Wat contains many astronomically inspired symbols and alignments. One study suggests that the temple is aligned for favorable viewing of sunrise on the spring equinoxes, which like Tenochtitlan rises above a tower and therefore requires a slight tilt of the building for optimum viewing of winter and equinox sunrises (Kelley and Milone, 2005). The astronomer Robert Stencel reported many numerological coincidences between the dimension of the structure and the key numbers in the Hindu timekeeping system by drawing lines within the complex connecting major structures (Stencel, 1976). When the dimensions were expressed in units of 0.435 m (which was the assumed size of the Cambodian cubit or hat) Stencel found that the temple included dimensions corresponding ...” (Penprase, 2010).

Voûte and Long Archaeoastronomy

When reporting the discussion by Barnhart and Powell, we have evidenced a proposal by Long and Voûte of a calendrical role of the zenith passage of the sun, which is clear and simple, because it is related to counting the days between the zenith passages of the sun. Let us note that it exists a very

interesting review about Voûte and Long work, entitled “Alternative approaches to eighth-century Central Javanese Buddhist architecture” by Andrea Acri, 2011.

Acri writes that “the [Voûte and Long] book's most significant novelty is its emphasis on *archaeoastronomy, the study of ancient cultures' astronomical knowledge*. Voûte and Long demonstrate that the monument embeds an encoded (mainly, but not exclusively, numerical) symbolism based on the movement of celestial bodies such as Sun, Moon and asterisms of the zodiac. The builders of Borobudur 'embraced a "sacred science" that did not perceive any separation between the spiritual practice of Buddhism and Hinduism and the scientific disciplines of astronomy, *chronology*, cosmology, geometry and the higher mathematics' (p. 2). ... As John Miksic (1990:45) has acknowledged, the Borobudur expresses 'a complex message in a code that has yet to be cracked'. Voûte and Long have produced a fascinating attempt to crack the code of Borobudur - a monument that, according to them, can be understood only if we assume that its builders had an advanced scientific and geographical knowledge” (Acri, 2011).

“The authors convincingly argue ... [that] important cultural and religious values were attributed to the regular celestial phenomena observed in the sky, among which is the cycle of the Sun through the day, months (in the form of equinoxes and solstices) and years (in the form of its almost imperceptible westwards shift through the zodiacal houses known as precession of the equinoxes). In this respect, the authors' approach appears to owe much to the erudite yet controversial study on ancient mythology by Giorgio de Santillana and Hertha von Dechend, *Hamlet's mill* (1969), as well as to Eleanor Mannikka's *Angkor Wat: Space; time and kingship* (1996)” (Acri, 2011).

“Applying the principles of archaeoastronomy to central Javanese architecture, the authors argue that Borobudur functioned as a calendrical monument, fixing in stone certain regular astronomical phenomena and thereby becoming a 'mirror' of the heavens. It was also a device for calculating time, namely a gigantic gnomon that calculated the hours in a day (vitaly important for the daily life of Buddhist monks), the months, equinoxes and solstices in a solar year (useful for ceremonial and ritual purposes), and the much longer cosmic cyclical eras known in Sanskrit culture as yugas. The authors argue that, in order to properly understand the meaning and function of the monument, it must be studied against the background of its geographical position and setting, dominated by the imposing silhouettes of two volcanoes and ranges of hills. The surroundings of Borobudur, they conclude, are as important and significant as the monument itself for they provide the scope for certain astronomical alignment” (Acri, 2011).

And then, in Acri 2011, we can find mentioned “numerology”: “Voûte and Long draw attention to recurring, and thus 'meaningful' (that is, non-coincidental) numbers embedded in many architectural elements of the monument itself. Consider, for instance, the **72** stupas on the summit, the **504** jina images (**432 [4 x 108]** on top of the four gallery balustrades + 72 on the summit), the 1460 (365 x 4) narrative panels, and so on. Previous scholars have tried to connect these significant numbers with elements of Buddhist doctrine traceable to Sanskrit texts, whereas our authors understand them as an attempt by the ancient builders to harmoniously link the microcosmos to the macrocosmos by means of numerical correspondences between architectural elements and solar and lunar months, years and longer cosmic eras. I [Acri] have found most of their reasoning in this regard to be plausible and well argued” (Acri, 2011).

Let us add also a study which is linking Borobudur to sky, proposed by Nabila et al., 2022: “Relief IVB-66 relates to the constellation of Ursa Major”. “The calculation of equatorial-horizontal coordinate transformations shows that the Pleiades star cluster is 41.28° higher than Ursa Mayor constellation in 800 AD. Therefore, the relief IVB-66 on Borobudur Temple based on the Gandavyuha story relates to the Pleiades star cluster.” “This finding enriches the evidence of the use of the Pleiades star cluster in Ancient Javanese society and the use of the Borobudur Temple stupas as a daily time marker” (Nabila et al., 2022).

Fingerprints

As we are here discussing numbers in architecture and landscape, we cannot avoid mentioning the Fingerprints of the Gods, by Graham Hancock. In this manner, we can appreciate at a glance what we have previously reported from Acri, 2011. Here in the following some passages.

“According to Professor de Santillana, this type of uniformity suggests a guiding hand at work. In Hamlet’s Mill, a seminal and original thesis on ancient myth written in collaboration with Hertha von Dechend (professor of the History of Science at Frankfurt University) he argues that:

universality is in itself a test when coupled with a firm design. When something found, say, in China, turns up also in Babylonian astrological texts, then it must be assumed to be relevant if it reveals a complex of uncommon images which nobody could claim had risen independently by spontaneous generation. Take the origin of music. Orpheus and his harrowing death may be a poetic creation born in more than one instance in diverse places. But when characters who do not play the lyre but blow pipes get themselves flayed alive for various absurd reasons, and their identical end is rehearsed on several continents, ... it can hardly be a coincidence ... Likewise, when one finds numbers like 108, or 9×13 reappearing under several multiples in the Vedas, in the temples of Angkor, in Babylon, in Heraclitus’ dark utterances, and also in the Norse Valhalla, it is not accident ...

Connecting the great universal myths of cataclysm, is it possible that such coincidences that cannot be coincidences, and accidents that cannot be accidents, could denote the global influence of an ancient, though as yet unidentified, guiding hand? ... According to Santillana and von Dechend, all such images refer to celestial events and do so, furthermore, in the refined technical language of an archaic but ‘immensely sophisticated’ astronomical and mathematical science: ‘This language ignores local beliefs and cults. It concentrates on numbers, motions, measures, overall frames, schemas—on the structure of numbers, on geometry.’” (Hancock, 1995).

About precession: “These, Sellers believes, constitute the basic ingredients of a precessional code which appears again and again, with eerie persistence, in ancient myths and sacred architecture. In common with much esoteric numerology, it is a code in which it is permissible ... The pre-eminent number in the code is 72. To this is frequently added 36, making 108, and it is permissible to multiply 108 by 100 to get 10,800 or to divide it by 2 to get 54, which may then ...” (Hancock, 1995). “Archaeo-astronomer Jane B. Sellers, who studied Egyptology at the University of Chicago’s Oriental Institute, spends her winters in Portland, Maine, and summers at Ripley Neck, a nineteenth-century enclave ‘downcast’ on Maine’s rocky coast” (Hancock, 1995).

Sellers is Jane B. Sellers, author of “The Death of Gods in Ancient Egypt”.

About Angkor, we can find it investigated by archaeoastronomer J. B. Seller: “Nor does it seem that Sellers’s ‘code’ is confined to mythology. In the jungles of Kampuchea the temple complex of Angkor looks as though it could have been purpose-built as a precessional metaphor. It has, for example, five gates to each of which leads a road bridging the crocodile-infested moat that surrounds the whole site. Each of these roads is bordered by a row of gigantic stone figures, 108 per avenue, 54 on each side (540 statues in all) and each row carries a huge Naga serpent. Furthermore, as Santillana and von Dechend point out in Hamlet’s Mill, the figures do not ‘carry’ the serpent but are shown to ‘pull’ it, which indicates that these 540 statues are ‘churning the Milky Ocean’. The whole of Angkor ‘thus turns out to be a colossal model set up with true Hindu fantasy and incongruousness’ to express the idea of precession.” (Hancock, 1995).

I am here reporting about Sellers, Santillana and von Dechend. Let me stress that I DO NOT consider number 108 linked to precession. This must be clear to everybody: I do not consider 108 linked to precession. It is clear for all the discussion here proposed.

In Hancock, 1995, we can find also that “In the Hebrew Cabala there are 72 angels through whom the Sephiroth (divine powers) may be approached, or invoked, by those who know their names and numbers. Rosicrucian tradition speaks of cycles of 108 years (72 plus 36) ... Similarly the number 72 and its permutations and subdivisions are of great significance to the Chinese secret societies known as Triads. ...” (Hancock, 1995).

Borobudur and the supposed alignment of temples

We find told in Wikipedia that "During the restoration in the early 20th century, it was discovered that three Buddhist temples in the region, Borobudur, Pawon and Mendut, are positioned along a straight line. A ritual relationship between the three temples must have existed, although the exact ritual process is unknown". References are Krom, 1927, Moens, 1952

Fig. 10: Map Courtesy: ACME Mapper. From Mendut (T) to Pawon (U), pilgrims must cross two rivers.

In December 2017, I wrote in my [The Zenith Passage of the Sun at Candi Borobudur](#), the following abstract: “Here we discuss the link of the 72 stupas on the top platform of the Borobudur temple to the number of days between the solstice and the zenith passage of the sun. This link is strengthened by the recent find of an alignment of Borobudur and the satellites Mendut and Pawon temples,”

Further discussions are necessary about the temples’ alignment.

“Chandi Borobudur is not the only monument in the area. The region was formerly strewn with temple buildings, as is evident from the fact no fewer than thirty sites have been found within a radius of 5 kilometres around it. It is notable that nearly all of them are Hindu. Only **Borobudur, Pawon, Mendut and Ngawen** are Buddhist” (Amon, 2005). Then, we have four temples, not three.

- 1) **Not as straight as believed** - Amon, 2005: “In 1998, Long conducted a GPS survey of the area that allowed him to gather the requisite data for determining the precise azimuth bearing of the Borobudur-Pawon-Mendut alignment. He discovered that the line was not nearly as straight as T. van Erp had thought. With respect to Borobudur, the temples of Pawon and Mendut are actually separated by an azimuth angle that is in excess of 17 minutes of arc. Therefore, the line Borobudur-Pawon points at a different spot on the eastern horizon from the Borobudur-Mendut alignment”. This is the same for the western horizon, of course.
- 2) **Mount Merapi** - “The Japanese scholar Eiji Hattori points out that the reasons behind the initial selection of a site for Borobudur can only be understood by ascending to the summit to watch the Sun rise right behind Mount Merapi even as the first of its rays are hitting Borobudur while the plain below is still shrouded in darkness. Purely by accident this is exactly what Long had encountered during his

first visit to Central Java. Did the builders also have a Mount Merapi sunrise in mind when they chose the site and initially laid out their construction plans?” (Amon, 2005).

Fig.11: Borobudur, Pawon, Mendut and Ngawen alignment. Maps Courtesy Google Maps. In [Wikipedia](#), about Ngawen, we can find mentioned this alignment.

Fig.12: Courtesy Google Earth

- 3) “According to Eiji Hattori, **the importance of the Mount Merapi sunrise** lies in the fact that the dawn would have initially illuminated the central stupa at Borobudur’s summit prior to illuminating the rest of the kingdom. In one of his earlier publications, he even uses the expression ‘the dawn of serenity’ to describe Borobudur’s overall meaning. Hattori also believes that the images of the Buddha Vairocana that were installed on the top three levels of the monument were meant to represent the Sun. These images all display the ritual hand gesture or mudra known as the ‘turning of the wheel’ (dharmachakra), which itself is a solar symbol” (Amon, 2005).
- 4) “Borobudur is situated in the tropics at the latitude of 7.608° south. The Sun is north of that latitude for six months of each solar cycle, and south of it for the remaining six months. Under these conditions Borobudur is aligned with the sunrise behind Merapi on just two mornings each year. Using a PCbased computer astronomy program and assuming that the height of Mount Merapi at that time had indeed

been 2.10 kilometres, Long determined that the first **Borobudur - Mount Merapi** sunrise would have taken place on 25 or 26 April in the early ninth century CE, followed by a second performance on either 10 or 11 August. In the year 807 CE, for example, the two Merapi sunrises took place on 26 April and 11 August, or fifty-four days either side of the summer solstice date of 19 June in that particular year. Is it merely coincidental that Borobudur’s layout features a similar 54—54 split in the number of Buddha images installed to either side of its four axis stairways?” (Amon, 2005).

- 5) Long investigates the path of the Sun during the day. “He found that the Borobudur-Mendut alignment coincided with the sunrise on two days of the solar year, the first of which occurred in early April during the late eighth and early ninth centuries CE. The April sunrise always coincided with the Sun’s entry into the **zodiac constellation Aries, the ‘Ram’**. The astronomers of India called this point the ‘First of Aries’ because it defined the start of the entire celestial sphere. According to them, this was the very point in the sky where all the planets entered into an alignment at the start of each and every “World Age’.” (Amon, 2005).
- 6) **Borobudur-Mahameru** - Tanudirjo, 2013. « Mount Mahameru, the centre of the Universe and the adobe of the gods. According to Hindu-Buddhist cosmology, this sacred mountain is encircled by concentric rings of sea and land. Recent geological research in the vicinity of Borobudur (Murwanto et al 2004). The occurrence of an ancient lake surrounding Borobudur was hypothesized by W.O.J. Niewenkamp more than 75 years ago (de Casparis 1981:70, 83). Its verification is indeed a strong indication that Borobudur was constructed to represent Mahameru. What is more, astronomical studies show that Borobudur, Mendut, and Pawon are arranged along an east-west axis pointing directly to the Merapi volcano to the east ...” (Tanudirjo, 2013).

“The ninth-century world-heritage Buddhist monument of Borobudur (Java, Indonesia) stands above the floor of a dried-out paleo-lake, but it remains uncertain as to whether it was ever constructed on a lake shore. Here we reveal through new chronological and paleo-environmental data on the extant sediment record of the area that Borobudur intentionally stood by an existing lake. For the first time, evidence of this conjunction validates quite literally the debated cosmological interpretation of the edifice as an aquatic lotus symbol upon which Buddha is seated. The fluctuating life history of the lake spanned at least 20 000 years” (Murwanto et al., 2004).

Topographic map courtesy [TessaDEM](#) . Two markers are indicating the position of Pawon (west of Progo) and Mendut (east of Progo).

- 7) “Many scholars have considered Borobudur to be closely linked with Mendut and Pawon, the three probably having been connected by a processional road crossing the Progo River. However, *neither aerial photographs nor terrain investigations have shown any traces of the paving of such a road, nor of any structures that might have been expected to have bordered it.* On the other hand, the same aerial photographs have shown traces that apparently reflect the ground plan and hidden foundations of *a fourth building near Bojang village, opposite Chandi Pawon and just across the Progo River.* This building, which has almost entirely disappeared over the course of time, is very similar to Chandi Pawon in dimensions and shape, and might be its twin. *The two [temples] may have been designed to guard the crossing of the Progo,* which especially during the rainy season can be very dangerous due to sudden flash floods.” (Amon, 2005).
- 8) **The temples Borobudur, Pawon and Mendut, are not considered as in alignment with each other** - Huu Phuoc Le (2010). “According to Y. Iwamoto and Daigoro Chihara, Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut might have been conceived as a group to form a sacred pilgrimage path or as a conceptual map leading to the location of the Sailendras’ royal palace. They theorized that as Mendut faced northwest and Borobudur faced northeast and the place where these diagonal lines intersected could be the location of the buried royal palace; ... In reality Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut do not lie on the same east-west axis but rather in the northwesterly direction while their entrances also have different orientations; therefore they are not considered as in alignment with each other. The theory is thus highly conjectural and without any factual supports.”
- 9) **The Ritual Procession at Borobudur** - In Soekmono, 1976, we can read that “According to oral tradition the triad [Mendut, Pawon and Borobudur] was once linked by a paved processional path, flanked by richly decorated balustrades. Unfortunately, land and aerial surveys so far carried out have produced *no convincing evidence of this.* Some hewn stones found in the fields east of the village of Borobudur many decades ago are supposed to be remains of the pavement. Further evidence is still lacking.” (Soekmono, 1976). “The sequence followed by the pilgrim in ancient times remains the same for the present-day visitor. The normal route to Chandi Borobudur, either from Yogyakarta or from Magelang, passes Chandi Mendut anyway, so that the first monument which emerges before reaching Chandi Borobudur is Chandi Mendut. Chandi Pawon, however, is reached by a side-way, since *the present road does not follow the ancient processional path.*” (Soekmono, 1976)

We do not know the way the pilgrim followed in ancient times. Therefore, a supposed archaeoastronomical alignment cannot have any evidential value of a processional path. Moreover, “aerial photographs have shown traces” of a fourth building, that, with Pawon temple, was guarding the cross of Progo river (Amon, 2005).

“The exceptional composition of the triad has led to much speculation about the relation between Chandi Borobudur, Chandi Pawon and Chandi Mendut. The most plausible link is religious, if the denomination ‘compound’ is interpreted in a particular way; the three monuments can be taken as a whole to represent one religious conception” (Soekmono, 1976). Please note that, in the following discussion, we will further mention the rituals and that a study exists which is considering the alignment of four temple, and not of three temples.

According to Soekmono, 1976, “The assumption that the pilgrim had to pass Chandi Pawon as he made his way from Chandi Mendut to Chandi Borobudur along the paved processional path *might suggest* that Chandi Pawon was a kind of station *on the long journey*; after being purified through the required ceremonies of worship at Chandi Mendut, Chandi Pawon allowed him to pause and reflect before proceeding on the pilgrimage to Chandi Borobudur where a tiresome series of circumambulations awaited”. No information in Soekmono about the time (one day or more days) the pilgrim spent in pilgrimage. It means that we have uncertainty at least of a day, in the case that we assume the supposed processional road intentionally oriented to the sunset on the days of the zenith passage of the sun. Let us stress that no link exists to Vesak (see Chia, 2020). But the temples of the worship complex could

have been four, and a direction according to the sunset on the day of the zenith passage is questionable, as we will show in the following.

- 10) **Moens and Long.** Of the study by Moens, translated by Long in 2007. I have already made some observations in [SSRN, 2024](#). If we consider in depth the Moens' descriptions of rituals which are regarding the local kings, we can see clearly that the rituals have nothing to do with pilgrimages. The Moens' text, 1951, is available at the following link <https://asisbiz.com/Indonesia/Barabudur-Mendut-Pawon.pdf>. Let me strongly suggest the reader to appreciate the complexity of Moens' rituals, directly in his text translated into English. Rituals are regarding the funeral of the king (west), and the enthronement of his son (east-zenith). Therefore, we have at least two rituals that were made in different periods of time for sure, being one linked to the death of the king, and the second in the resurrection of the king in his son.

Here are some passages from an article (Izza and Munandar, 2017), mentioning Moens. "The first study on Borobudur was conducted during the Dutch East Indies era by Van Erp and N. J. Kroom, which coincided with the temple's restoration project (Ramelan et al., 2013, p. 27). The study indicated an association between Borobudur Temple and two other temples located nearby, namely Pawon Temple and Mendut Temple. This was based on the similarities with regard to the architectural style and ornamentation of the three temples, indicating that they were built in the same period, that is, the Sailendra dynasty era (Moens, 2007, p. 2). The next study was conducted by J. L. Moens in the 1950s (2007, pp. 93–99), which connected the three temples with Banon Temple, a Hindu temple located near Pawon Temple. Furthermore, it shows that Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut Temples were all ritual centers of Mahayana Buddhism, whereas Banon Temple was a place for the followers of Siwa-Siddhanta. Another study conducted by IGN Anom imaginarily connected Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut Temples, showing that the three temples were built along a straight line (Anom, 2005: 28). Totok Roesmanto also conducted a study on the location of Borobudur and the other temples surrounding it (2011: 99–120), which shows that the three temples are positioned along a single straight line, which was organized during the construction of Mendut Temple. It is also shown that the imaginary line connecting the three temples is linked to Mount Merapi." (Izza and Munandar, 2017, see please references given by them in their article).

- 11) **Four temples** - Let us concentrate on the article by Izza and Munandar, 2017, about the alignment of **four** temples, given in the following maps (Borobudur, Pawon, Mendut, Ngawen). Izza and Munandar, in 2017, displayed the association of Borobudur Temple with the surrounding Buddhist temples. "Several studies have been conducted by scholars and experts, and according to one of them, Borobudur Temple is associated with other temples, such as Pawon and Mendut Temples". However, they add, according to their specific and accurate archaeological research, the Ngawen temple.

At <https://www.taylorfrancis.com> we can find the article by Izza and Munandar. The authors "offer a new interpretation on Borobudur and its surrounding temples as a cohesive unit for sacred procession. Factors such as location, religious background, ornaments, and statues are common in Borobudur and Ngawen Temples. ... The collected data were then applied in the context of the Mataram Kuno (Ancient Mataram) period using a religious framework. The last step encompasses interpretation of the data". Authors believe that their study "will provide a new interpretation on the roles of Borobudur and the surrounding Buddhist temples as monuments for sacred procession in the ancient times" (Izza and Munandar, 2017). The Borobudur Temple "possesses several meanings related to the belief of Mahayana Buddhism. Moreover, in the past, Borobudur had served as the center of other sacred buildings surrounding it (Huntington, 1994, p.136). Within a distance of 5 km around the temple, there are three other temples affiliated with Mahayana Buddhism, among which are Pawon Temple (1,150 m from Borobudur) and Mendut (2,900 m) (Kaelan, 1959: 122). Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut Temples are located in the west of Elo River, and Ngawen is, in fact, located in the east side of the river, which is, in turn, 4 km away from Borobudur" (Izza and Munandar, 2017) [see please the Google map given above].

“According to previous studies, Borobudur, Pawon, and Mendut Temples are positioned on a straight line and they form a triadic (a group of three) of sacred buildings affiliated to Mahayana Buddhism. However, according to Totok Roesmanto (2011, pp. 99–120), *the imaginary axis connecting the three temples is not a straight line*, and it is interpreted that they were the centers of religious rituals and processions in the past. Furthermore, it is suggested that the three temples were closely associated with Mount Merapi. Nevertheless, further examination of the map shows an addition temple called Ngawen Temple, from which a parallel imaginary axis can also be drawn, connecting it to the other three temples. Thus, on the basis of this fact, it can be interpreted that, in the past, the procession of the religious rituals might begin in Ngawen Temple and end in Borobudur” (Izza and Munandar, 2017).

“To conclude, Borobudur, Pawon, Mendut, and Ngawen Temples are located adjacent to each other and connected by an imaginary axis. Ornamentation style in Ngawen Temple shows a similarity among the four temples. The shapes of statues in Borobudur and Ngawen are also similar. Therefore, we may conclude that Borobudur is not only associated with Pawon and Mendut, but also correlates with Ngawen Temple in terms of religious affiliation, positioning, ornamentation style, and iconography as well as the structures that were used as locations for sacred Buddhist rituals during the Ancient Mataram era. *In addition to the association of Borobudur and the other temples, the association between Borobudur and Mount Merapi and the hills surrounding the temple is observed.* More studies need to be conducted on Bubrah, Lumbung, and Sewu Temples. The similarities and the different patterns of association among Bubrah, Lumbung, Sewu Temples as well as the association between the Buddhist temples around Borobudur and those around Sewu Temple need to be studied” (Izza and Munandar, 2017).

Therefore, Borobudur can be associated with the eastern sunrise sky and Mount Merapi, not only to the western sunset sky.

Suggested reading: Origin and Significance of Borobudur

It is important to analyze the dissertation by Kandahjaya, 2004, “A study on the origin and significance of Borobudur”. “To date there has been no solid answer yet to many fundamental problems of Borobudur. We still do not know what Borobudur is, why the builders built it, nor even the meaning of its name. Conclusive support for any particular interpretation is still to be found. In the past the most frequent method for understanding Borobudur has been to examine the reliefs and their symbolism, and on that basis to identify a text or set of texts as the source for the construction of the monument. On the basis of such an approach, scholars have debated whether Borobudur is a memorial {stupa} or a diagram of the cosmos {mandala}. Such speculations, however, have failed for two reasons. First, they fail to take into account an epigraphic record known as the Kayumwungan inscription from central Java dated to 824. ... Employing a multi-disciplinary approach, among them historical, philological, and visual, this dissertation attempts to demonstrate three claims: (1) that the Sanskrit portion of the Kayumwungan inscription narrates events leading to the consecration of Borobudur and thereby describes the origin of Borobudur, including its architectural model, modifications, organizing themes, meaning, and function: (2) that the architectural model of Borobudur was a penthouse {kutagara} of the Buddha Sakyamuni as described in the Lalitavistara-sutra, and that (3) the meaning of the name “Borobudur” is “an excellent Buddha-image” {buddha-rupa}, and that this meaning correlates both with the description in the Kayumwungan inscription and with the architectural model of Borobudur” (Kandahjaya, 2004).

To conclude, we have seen that numbers are fundamental in architecture at Java and Cambodia. Being the numbers intrinsic in the temples of Borobudur and Angkor Wat, their numerology cannot be a “modern construct”. We have provided many references about the zenith passage of the sun and its role in Java, Cambodia and Maya lands. Several archaeoastronomical alignments are present in literature. However, alignments are details in the overall planning of the sites.

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